

Information and Communication Technology Skills Acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated Information and Communication Technology skills acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. Four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. The researcher adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 235 Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Rivers State University while sample of 235 student respondents was drawn through census sampling technique. Information and Communication Technology Skills for Entrepreneurship Development Questionnaire was used for data collection. Validity of the instrument was determined by five experts in the Department of Business Education, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained through Cronbach method. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. The findings of the study among others revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5 while the hypotheses revealed that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU students and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. It was recommended among others that teachers should expose Office Management and Technology students to transaction processing skills for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Keywords: ICT, Entrepreneurship, Transaction, Decision Support, Hardware and Software

INTRODUCTION

The advancement in science and technology no doubt has brought about series of reforms in various aspects of entrepreneurship activities as well as the human life. Innovations in science and technology have simplified the process of business relations as well as task performance. Technology has made business profit possible as a result of the expansion in science and technology which has given

entrepreneurs several new face lift in business activities. This technology influences the overall activities of learners known as Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) deals with the use of appropriate technological devices for carrying out business activities in the social world. Similarly, ICT skills are required for collecting, utilizing and disseminating information to the students, customers and for businesses alike in every organization. The essence of using ICT in an organization is to ensure that information is provided to the users timely and accurately. The relevance of ICT to the success of the business environment promotes its use by Office Management and Technology students of universities for entrepreneurship. This gave rise to innovations and development of modern business organizations.

Consequently, everything possible needs to be done to entrench students' knowledge of entrepreneurship in public universities both in products and business operations as well as services. Not until this is achieved, the goals and target of university education in Nigeria will remain practically a ruse. No expensive approach to entrench and assure quality in our universities is costlier than having university graduates or system with deficiencies (Njoku, 2016). The approach Njoku seems to be advocating is the use of ICT and its support tools. As noted by Williams (2016), ICT is a quality based system that guarantees efficiency, cost reduction, energy saving, accuracy, flexibility, convenience and lots more.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a modern concept that has attracted enormous attention globally. It has been defined by different people in different ways. Wikipedia, the internet free encyclopedia defined it as a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate, create, disseminate, store and manage information. They include computers, internet, broadcasting technologies like radio, television, telephony and so on. According to Achuonye (2017), ICT is a means of accessing or receiving, storing, transferring processing and sending ideas, perceptions and information through computers and telecommunication facilities. It is a convergence of computer networking and telecommunication.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been proven very supportive and facilitative towards organising and managing entrepreneurship education in general and university education particular. Curtis and Cobham (2019) defined Information and communication technology (ICT) as any system that provides information for the management of entrepreneurship activities carried out within an educational setting. McNurlin and Sprague (2014) perceived ICT as a computerised system designed for generating essential information in order to aid school managers and other users perform their duties for entrepreneurship educational development and improvement. Mariott (2016) defined it as a system that generates accurate, timely and organizes information so that education managers and other users can make decisions, solve problems, supervise activities and track the Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development.

According to Joseph (2014), ICT is a system through which information is generated for business oriented issues and activities. Stallings (2015) described ICT as an all-encompassing designation for systems that assist students and managers of schools in making decision. It is a system for organizing information in a systematic way for the management of entrepreneurship development. It is responsible for collection, processing, analysing, publication, distribution, rendering information services for users of educational information. Again, ICT is responsible for providing information that is required of students within the entrepreneurship system for policy planning, implementation, decision making, monitoring and evaluation (Joseph, 2014).

Curtis and Cobham (2019) described a system as a collection of interrelated parts that form a whole. David and Stuart (2014), defined a system as an assemblage or combination of things or parts forming a complex or unitary whole. The essential point in the definition above is that a system is a collection of interrelated parts or assemblage or combination of things or parts. Thus, it cannot be a single thing but must be perceived as having an internal structure, Moreover, these parts must be dynamically interrelated through change rather than close proximity.

The system must also have some purpose, goal or objective, and the changes or processes in its parts will normally sense the necessary skills to achieve goals. All ICT skills have objectives which must be specified. Thus, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills have clear specified objective

of producing information for management of entrepreneurship activities such as financial computation and record, staff and clients information management, teaching and learning, researches, publication of notice, decision making and so on (Curtis & Cobham, 2019).

Lucas (2018) said that information is data processed for entrepreneurs that deal with a wide variety of data, some of this concerns financial transactions. An example of an item of transaction data is the record of purchases and sales of commodities. This fact might be recorded on a piece of paper, such as in a receipt book or as a series of laser-bummed impressions on a compact disk. Information is different from data. Whereas information is a processed data, data, on the other hand, is the raw material or the record of an event or a fact from which information can be derived. The information derives from this data is used for making decisions, of which planning decisions and control decisions are most important (Curtis & Cobhan 2019). Worthy of note is that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) system produces information for management of activities at all levels.

Transaction Processing Skill for Entrepreneurship in Rivers State

Joseph (2014) emphasized that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) should be often integrated with transaction processing systems skill (TPS). Siddique (2017) described transaction process systems as a system that captures and process data generated during an organization's day-to-day transaction. A transaction processing is a method where each transaction is carried out immediately by direct interaction between the operator and the system. It is used when information held in the computer is up-to-date. For example, an entrepreneur has to attend a meeting in Abuja, which requires flights and accommodation. He does not want to arrive at the airport to find too many people have been booked and there are not enough seats on the plane or that two families have been booked into the same room at the hotel. He can simply click on his computer search for the computerized Reservation Service where checks for availability and a booking is made and recorded immediately.

Clerical member of staff typically perform the activities associated with transaction processing which include the following; recording social and economic activities and data related to the organisation. It can also be used in making schedule, sending and receiving invoice from across members of the university community (Fisher, 2015).

Decision Support Skill for Entrepreneurship in Rivers State

Joseph (2014) said Decision Support System (DSS) is a system designed to help users reach a decision when a decision making situation arise. A variety of DSS exist to help with a range of decision. A decision support system (DSS) uses data from internal and/or external sources. Internal sources of data might include the number of staff employed, or students admitted, inventory or financial data from an organization data base. Data from external sources could include cost of materials, building, hostels for students, staff and other investments (Ekhaguere, 2016).

Similarly, Wischhusen and Scales (2014) opined that it was perfectly possible to make decisions in business prior to computerization, but: because a computer handles data, especially large volumes of data, so quickly, it is a very important tool in decision making in the modern business world, and very crucial in today extremely competitive market. For instance, to effect a pay rise of the organizational staff may require the use of computer to know the difference between the income and expenditure. This will help to decide whether or not to continue with such plan. Therefore it is appropriate to conclude that decision support system relies partly on the business database to be functional. Some other occasions, DSS becomes functional by the use of designated software (Wischhusen & Scales, 2014).

Neumann (2019) viewed Information and Communication Technology (ICT) for entrepreneurship as a collection of hardware, software, database and the internet resources that are designed to generate information that supports the day-today, short-range and long range business activities of the system users in a given setting. Neumann maintained that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is specially designed for business and educational activities as information generated served as management resources for managers and all users of educational information and entrepreneurs. From his view, it becomes understandable that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) involves generating information through the hardware, software and database.

Hardware Management Skill for Entrepreneurship in Rivers State

Curtis and Cobham (2019) perceived hardware as the physical components of a computer system, for example, circuits, keyboards, disk drives, disks and printers. Wischhussen and Scales (2014) described hardware as devices such as computers, terminals (devices that transmit and receive information) and peripheral equipments such as printers, etc. Carysforth (2014) identified hardware of a computer system consists of:

Input devices - used to put the information into the system, the Central Processing Unit (CPU) - the 'brains of the system which carries out all the instructions received (either from the operator or from the program), Storage devices - used to save both data and programs and Output devices used to display the end results (Curtis & Cobham, 2019). As noted by Williams (2016), ICT is a quality based system in that guarantees efficiency, cost reduction, time and energy saving, accuracy, flexibility, convenience and lots more.

Scanner

Curtis and Cobham (2019) perceived a scanner as a desktop device used to produce a document image. The document is placed on a glass plate and an image is optically captured by passing a bright light across source document. The image is converted into a digital bit-map, an array of Is and Os, and transmitted to a computer, where it can be stored in memory and later edited, if required, and saved. A scanner translated graphics, words or symbols on a printed page into digital signals that are recognised by the computer. Scanners are of two types flatbed and handheld. A flatbed scanner scan a document by placing the document face down on a flatbed of glass and the lid is closed. Handheld scanner performs the same job as flatbed of glass and the lid is closed. Handheld scanners perform the same job as flatbed scanners, but as they are usually on a few centimetres wide, the amount of information that can be scanned is limited. They are rolled across the document to be scanned, but the image produced is generally of a poorer quality to that produced by a flatbed scanner. These are used in computerized filing systems to input information from documents which have been received by an administrator (Carysforth, 2014).

Optical Character Readers

It entails the reading of reprinted characters on documents. These documents are 'passed through an optical character reader, which optically detects the characters on the document and convert them, to code, which is sent to the CPU. Some universities, business organizations and Jamb sell both processing and access cards which are designed for optical character readers.

Central Processing Unit

The key role of the central processing unit is to carry out instructions within the software, handle control, signals and perform arithmetic and logic operations. For example, the logic unit of CPU can carry out arithmetic operations like to add two numbers together while logic unit can compare two numbers to establish which is the larger. The CPU also contains main memory whose purpose is to store programs during their execution, store data that is being used by the current programs; and store the operating system (i.e software and applications).

Optical Mark Readers

Wishhusen and Scales (2014) opined that optical mark reader is a scanning device that reads pencil marks from a specially designed form or document. It is often used for questionnaires multiple-choice answer sheets and even the national lottery. It can be employed by the universities for marking computer-based sheets. According to them, it scans sheets and the computer is able to process and analyse the students' results very quickly.

Magnetic Ink Character Readers

Magnetic ink character recognition is a method of data entry widely used in banking system for customers' cheques. Each cheque has identifying information (cheque number, account code and bank sort code) printed in magnetic ink in the lower left-hand corner (Curtis & Cobham, 2019).

Magnetic Stripe Reader

It magnetically reads information about the user's account stored on L the black stripe of a magnetic card. To check the identity of the user, the user is asked to enter his personal identification number (PIN) and

the computer compares the PIN with the stored data. Universities can purchase goods and receive payment from students and other debtors by using MSR (Lucas, 2018).

Bar-Code Readers

Bar codes are now familiar as part of the printed packaging on supermarket products. They are also embossed on every standard academic textbook in the university's library. A bar-code consists of a series of thick and thin black bars divided by thick and thin spaces printed on a light-coloured background. These bars correspond to digits, which are also printed underneath the bar-codes (Williams, 2016), further added that groups of bars represent individual digits and that most bar-codes are made up of 12-13 digits. Two digits indicate the country of origin of the products, five digits indicate the manufacturer, and the remaining digit is used L for checking that the other digits have been read correctly by the device reading the bar code. In university system, library ticketing can be carried out using bar-code readers. In doing this, students' library tickets can be printed with bar-codes on them. The bar-code on each student's ticket recognises him or her as a member of the library and the bar-code on the book identifies a particular copy of the book. When a student borrows a library book, both his and or her ticket and book are scanned. The library computer system can then match the borrower with the book. This enables the system to keep track of book on loan and to generate letters automatically to members that their books are overdue (Bishop, 2014).

Tracker Ball

A track ball, sometimes called a roller-ball is like upside down mouse that allows the user to point and select items on screen by rotating the ball with the fingertips, rather than pushing a mouse around a desktop. It requires very little space to operate and is often used with CAD software. It is also commonly built into laptop computers in place of the conventional mouse. A tracker ball or roller-ball performs the same function as a mouse (Bishop, 2014).

Digital Camera

A digital camera is similar in appearance to a normal camera and capture still images. Rather than using photographic film, the images are stored in memory inside the camera and later transferred to a computer. The digital camera has the advantage that pictures of poor quality and immediately be deleted and replaced (Curtis & Cobham, 2019). Similarly, digital camera as the modern camera which has a facility that enable the user to view the image on a small liquid crystal display (LCD) screen built into the camera. This is very different to a traditional camera where the image is recorded on film that must be processed before the image can be viewed.

Digital camcorder works in a similar way, but the video footage is stored on a small camcorder tape. Video-editing software makes it possible to edit the footage in a professional way by adding voiceovers, special effects, titles or fading in and out of scenes. Another type of digital is the Webcam (World Wide Web Camera). A webcam automatically records an image very so often rather than continuously. These digital cameras have many uses, especially in university education as they can be used to generate Information and monitor examination, meeting, conference and other academic related proceedings (Wischhusen & Scales, 2014).

Similarly, Wischhusen and Scales (2014) were of the view that EMIS support tools such as digital or wireless cameras can generate information on students' examination behaviour and the conduct of examinations generally. Students' attendance needs not to be written down on paper as the wireless cameras can capture the full image of each student while aiming his entry into the exam hall on a one-by one basis. They can 'also capture and store the images of students who turn out late for exams, during the exam, the cameras can monitor students in exam halls and expose any of them indulging in exam mal practice (Njoku, 2016). Information on exam problems such as lack of adequate space and time clash are generated for official decisions to be taken to tackle them (Njoku, 2016).

Touch Screen

A touch screen allows the user to interact with the computer by L touching the screen on a display menu. This breaks an infrared light beam and generates an electronic signal that identifies the location on the screen. Touch screens can be used to access the internet and sent C mails by the university staff and students (Sloane, 2016).

Graphics Tablet

A graphics table sometimes called a digitizing table or digitizer is used for freehand drawing and sketching and is especially useful for tracing drawings. It is used along with a cursor (puck) and/or a pen (Stylus). The tablet contains electrodes that detect the movement of cursor or stylus and the movements are translated into digital signals that are sent to the computer. A digital pen is being developed that will be able to transfer handwritten text to the computer, internet and mobile phones. Entrepreneurs can apply or generate information through the graphics tablet (Carrysfort, 2014).

Microphone

Microphones are sensors that detect sound. Some microphones are used with voice recognition equipment that translates spoken words into digital signals for the computer. If the user wanted to use voice recognition software, it would probably be necessary to record the user's commands (information details) several times over so that the computer is able to recognise the user's spoken voice and respond. Business lectures can be delivered by the use of microphones (keen, 2017).

Sensors

A sensor is a device that reacts to certain physical conditions such as light, sound or movement. The data is not entered manual by via the keyboard or mouse. Instead, an electronic signal registering the current condition or state is sent to the computer and if necessary, the computer program with respond. Sensors are good for the security departments of universities and for safety of the staff students and facilities and equipment (Espejo, Schuumann, Schwanninger & Bilello, 2016).

At this juncture, the submission of Wischhusen and Scales (2014) becomes imperative. According to them, before one can understand how and why organisations use ICT, one needs to be aware of the different types of organisations, how they are structured, the typical department and what functions of those department is.

Curtis and Cobham (2019) and Wischhusen and Scales (2014) stressed that there are three (3) types of organisations namely:

- (i) Commercial Organisation
- (ii) Industrial organisations; and
- (iii) Public Service.

Commercial Organisation: They explained these as organisations that are into buying and selling goods and products.

Industrial Organisation: they noted that these organisations are ones that manufacture or produce goods.

Public Service: They took these to mean those organisations that render services to the members of the public. Examples are banks, universities, colleges, insurance and so on.

Wischhusen and Scales (2014) noted that large organisations as are divided into different departments which carry out four (4) main functions of business: sales, purchasing, finance and operations. These functions of business here constitute the administrative areas in which ICT are required for the administration of the organisations as businesses use ICT support tools. Wischhusen and Scales (2014) stressed that ICT can be used to:

1. Communicate effectively both internally and externally with people;
2. Manage and control a production process
3. Manage finance - including payroll, budgeting, forecasting, and transactions and reporting.
4. Manage stock control
5. Market products and services efficiently

In a globalized economy such as we have today, education is faced with challenges some of these are the multiple changes which occur almost simultaneously and swiftly. To grapple with these, there is the need to improve entrepreneurship educational techniques with the application of modern technological equipments. ICT being a peculiar concept in the modern world is a source of many innovations in our ever changing world. As such, its inclusion in education is necessary.

Software Management Skill for Entrepreneurship in Rivers State

Looking at sales as one of the important business areas, Curtis and Cobham (2019) was of the opinion that information pertaining to sale of business products for all members of the society can be generated and advertised via the ICT such as the internet or the intranet or the extranet. Such information for the sales is usually lodged into the website of the business organization concerned while the internet provides the platform for the public to access or use the information. Apart from this, these Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can provide an electronic platform for auction sales of materials such as fairly used vehicles, air conditioners, computers, photocopiers, furniture and so on. Again, these electronic platforms can allow organizations to advertise a sale of spaces or pieces of land for business transactions within the environment such business transactions may include banking, operation of filling stations, restaurant, printing, photography, typing, among others. Forms and other required documents can be filled or attached and sent electronically. So also, the notice of the offer and acceptance as pertaining to the sale can be executed electronically within a reasonable time. Sales decisions are accurately and quickly generated through these electronic platforms thereby foreclosing delay associated the paper-based processes.

Reference to Neumann (2019), Information and Communication Technology (ICT) includes software. Curtis and Cobham (2019), software is the general term for instruction that controls the operation of the computer. Wischhusen and Scales (2014) defined software as a set of instructions written to make the computer work. A computer cannot do anything on its own. Instructions are input by the user, through perhaps the keyboard or mouse, and the software reacts to these instructions. This is why the user should not blame the computer if things go wrong because the computer does what the user has told it to do (Wischhusen & Scales, 2014). Williams (2017) identified different types of software include: The ROM BIOS Chip, Operating systems and Application software

The ROM BIOS Chip

Wischhusen and Scales (2014) opined that the read-only memory chip is on the motherboard and contains the instructions that enable the computer to start up or boot. When the computer is turned on or restarted, it looks for the start-up instruction in the ROM BIOS chip. BIOS stands for Basic Input Output System and is a set of instructions that tells the computer how to handle the flow of information between the computer and its input and output. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools such as optical mark readers (OMRs) can be used for marking computer-based sheets. These scan the multiple choice answer sheets; computer software application spreadsheets are used to process students' result very quickly and the statement of result is sent to the e-mail of each of the students for him or her to access and view (Njoku, 2016). Continued that floppy disks, hard disks, magnetic tapes, compact disks, zip drives, pen drives, RAM chips, CD-ROM and so on which are at large to be used to store information that may be useful for teaching, learning and academic researches as well as for other business purposes.

Operating System

The operating systems are the software program through which all application programs run (William, 2016). The purpose of the operating system is to schedule tasks, recognise data input from the keyboard, mouse or sensor, keep track of her directories and files on the disks and control peripheral devices such as the printer. This makes the operating system the foundation on which applications software such as word processing and spreadsheet programs are built. The most common operating systems for personal computers (PCS) are MS-DOS and systems that use Windowing Environments such as Window 2000 or Window XP, Window '98'.

To average computer user, the advantage of window is its Graphical User Interface (GUI) which is a user friendly method of showing information screen graphically. It lets the user start programs, select menus, choose commands and other options by using the mouse to click on the menus or icons (Barrenechea, 2018). Business owners or entrepreneurs manage activities such as record keeping and tracking, finance, registration, procession and publication, sales and purchases among others. The last element is that the information so generated from ICT is usually used by managers and other users for business information.

Statement of the Problem

Information and Communication Technology usage is the key to successful operations of business organizations. However, many businesses are lagging behind in its operations due to poor Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills. Administratively, the use of old approach characterized by paper-based information collection, oral advertisement and sales of products with zero Information and Communication Technology enable is a problem in this era driven ICT. Financial and material procurements, records, conveyance of directives, new policies, rules and regulations, notice of meetings and staff records keeping and communication, interactions, registration, staff payment records, official decision making, youth service related information records, among others, are largely done or carried out manually with half hazard work.

Academic related activities and researches are equally organised in the same way with the same old approach. Teaching and learning, assignments, notice of academic activities and programmes, researches, academic library activities and operations, publishing and publication of students' academic results to some extent are basically on paper. As a result, some institutions or organizations have low business patronage. It is against this backdrop that this study investigated information and communication technology skills acquired by office management and technology postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study investigated Information and Communication Technology skills acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. find out the extent transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
2. examine the extent decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
3. ascertain the extent hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
4. investigate the extent software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the extent of transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?
2. What is the extent of decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?
3. What is the extent of hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?
4. What is the extent of software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses.

The following hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided this study

1. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education of Office Management and Technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Rivers State University RSU and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education of Office Management and Technology students on decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
3. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education of Office Management and Technology students on

- hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
4. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of Rivers State University RSU and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education of Office Management and Technology students on software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted descriptive survey research design for the study. The study area is Rivers State. The population of the study comprised all the 235 Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Rivers State University 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 session. The strata are 65 respondents from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and 170 respondents from Rivers State University. The sample of 235 student respondents representing 100% of the population was drawn through census sampling technique. Information and Communication Technology Skills for Entrepreneurship Questionnaire (ICTSEQ) was used for data collection. The instrument contains 20 items all structured on a 4 point rating scales of Very High Extent (VHE) 4 points, High Extent (HE) 3 points, Low Extent (LE) 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) 1 point respectively. Validity of the instrument was determined by three experts in the Department of Business Education, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The following reliabilities were determine through Cronbach method. Information and Communication Technology Skills for Entrepreneurship was 0.74, while 0.74, 0.78, 0.74, 0.73, were for transaction processing skill, decision support skill, hardware management skill and software management skill respectively. The instrument was administered to the respondents in their various institutions in Rivers State by the researcher with the help of two research assistants. Out of 235 questionnaire administered, 230 copies were properly filled and retrieved. The research questions were answered using mean (\bar{X}), standard deviation (Sd) and rank order statistics for all the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. The criterion mean of 2.50 was used.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 1: Mean (\bar{X}), Mean set (\bar{X} \bar{X}) Standard Deviation (Sd) and Rank Order (Rnk) Scores on the Extent of transaction Processing Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

S/N	ITEMS	RSU x 165	IAUE x 65	Xx 230	Sd	Rank	Dec
1.	Using internet to increase customers awareness of products influence entrepreneurship activities	2.80	2.64	2.75	1.03	5 th	HE
2.	Using electronic board seminar for training influence entrepreneurship activities	2.90	2.75	2.85	1.13	1 st	HE
3.	World wide web for online advertisement for communities influence entrepreneurship activities	2.77	2.89	2.81	1.10	2 nd	HE
4.	Interment telephony to reduce the risk of traveling influence entrepreneurship activities	2.76	2.77	2.76	1.09	4 th	HE
5.	Using e-mail for information dissemination influence entrepreneurship activities	2.71	3.05	2.81	1.05	2 nd	HE

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 1 results showed that the average mean scores of RSU students range between 2.71 and 2.90, while those of IAUE range between 2.64 and 3.05. The mean set average for both group of Students range between 2.75 and 2.85. Judging by the results, table 1 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of decision support skill acquired by office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 2: Mean (\bar{X}), Mean set (\bar{X} \bar{X}) Standard deviation (Sd) and Rank Order (Rnk) Scores on the Extent Decision Support Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

S/N	ITEMS	RSU x 165	IAUE x 65	Xx 230	Sd	Rank	Dec
6.	Using database software to generate instructions influence entrepreneurship activities	2.80	2.81	2.80	1.09	1 st	HE
7.	Using decision support system software to reduce product pirating influence entrepreneurship activities	2.65	2.90	2.71	1.15	4 th	HE
8.	Using excel software to prepare account ledger influence entrepreneurship activities	2.55	2.88	2.64	1.08	5 th	HE
9.	Graphics software usage to increase staff creativity influence entrepreneurship activities	2.76	2.91	2.80	1.09	1 st	HE
10	Decision support system software for board meetings influence entrepreneurship activities	2.75	2.70	2.74	1.11	3 rd	HE

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 2 results showed that the average mean scores of RSU students range between 2.55 and 2.80, while those of IAUE range between 2.70 and 2.91. The mean set average for both group of students range between 2.64 and 2.80. Judging by the results, table 2 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 3: *What is the extent of hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 3: Mean (\bar{X}), Mean set (\bar{X} \bar{X}) Standard deviation (Sd) and Rank Order (Rnk) Scores on the Extent Hardware Management Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

S/N	ITEMS	RSU x 165	IAUE x 65	xx 230	Sd	Rank	Dec
11.	Using UPS to backup computer from power failure influence entrepreneurship activities	2.78	2.97	2.81	1.08	1 st	HE
12.	The use of key board to input figures into computer influence entrepreneurship activities	2.64	2.78	2.66	1.15	4 th	HE
13.	Using scanner to convert hard copy material to soft copy influence entrepreneurship activities	2.56	2.85	2.61	1.08	5 th	HE
14.	Use of accessory cables to link computer components to another influence entrepreneurship activities	2.75	2.97	2.79	1.08	2 nd	HE
15.	Using speakers to hear DVD sound from the computer after seminar influence entrepreneurship activities	2.74	2.60	2.71	1.13	3 rd	HE

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 3 results showed that the average mean scores of RSU students range between 2.56 and 2.78, while those of IAUE students range between 2.60 and 2.97. The mean set average for both group of students range between 2.61 and 2.81. Judging by the results, table 3 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 4: *What is the extent of software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities?*

Table 4: Mean (\bar{X}), Mean set (\bar{X} \bar{X}) Standard deviation (Sd) and rank order (Rnk) Scores on the Extent Software Management Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

S/N	ITEMS	RSU x 165	IAUE x 65	Xx 230	Sd	Ran k	Dec
16.	Using spreadsheet for staff salaries preparation processes influence entrepreneurship activities	2.71	2.58	2.66	1.12	4 th	HE
17.	Using desktop publishing for business documentation influence entrepreneurship activities	2.88	2.78	2.84	1.16	1 st	HE
18.	Facilitators ability to organize online seminars for their customers influence entrepreneurship activities	2.68	2.97	2.79	1.09	2 nd	HE
19.	Using graphic software for staff training influence entrepreneurship activities	2.57	2.67	2.60	1.08	5 th	HE
20.	Using database software to generate instructions influence entrepreneurship activities	2.61	2.92	2.72	1.17	3 rd	HE

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 4 results showed that the average mean scores of RSU students range between 2.57 and 2.88, while those of IAUE students range between 2.58 and 2.97. The mean set average for both group of students range between 2.60 and 2.84. Judging by the results, table 4 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of office management and technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by office management and technology postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Table 5: Summary of t-test on difference in the Mean Rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology Students on Transaction Processing Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

Categories	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t- cri	Level of significance	Decision
RSU	165	2.78	1.04	228	0.24	1.96	0.05	Ho was Accepted
IAUE	65	2.82	1.15					

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 5 above showed that the t calculated value of 0.24 is less than the t critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 228. The null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Table 6: Summary of t-test on difference in the Mean Rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology Students on Decision Support Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

Categories	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-cri	Level of significance	Decision
RSU	165	2.70	1.10					
IAUE	65	2.84	1.09	228	0.85	1.96	0.05	Ho was Accepted

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 6 above revealed that the t calculated value of 0.85 is less than the t critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 228. The null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses 3

There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Table 7: Summary of t-test on difference in the Mean Rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology Students on Hardware Management Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

Categories	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-cri	Level of significance	Decision
RSU	165	2.69	1.10					
IAUE	65	2.83	1.09	228	1.74	1.96	0.05	Ho was Accepted

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 7 showed that the t calculated value of 1.74 is less than the t critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 228. The null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses 4

There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of office management and technology students on software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Table 8: Summary of t-test on difference in the Mean Rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology Students on Software Management Skill Acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate Students for Entrepreneurship Development in Rivers State Universities

Categories	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	t-cal	t-cri	Level of significance	Decision
RSU	165	2.69	1.09	228	0.58	1.96	0.05	Ho was Accepted
IAUE	65	2.78	1.15					

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 8 showed that the t calculated value of 0.58 is less than the t critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with the degree of freedom of 228. The null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of office management and technology students on software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Summary of Findings

1. Table 1 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities
2. Table 2 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities
3. Table 3 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.
4. Table 4 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent of software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities
5. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities
6. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities
7. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of office management and technology students on hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities
8. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Extent of Transaction Processing Skill for Entrepreneurship Development

Table 1 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. However, the respondents identified that using internet to increase customer’s awareness of products, using electronic board seminar for training, Worldwide Web for online advertisement for communities, interment telephony to reduce the risk of traveling and using e-mail for information dissemination, all influence entrepreneurship activities. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and

Technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

Extent of Decision Support Skill for Entrepreneurship Development

Table 2 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. However, the respondents identified that using database software to generate instructions, using decision support system software to reduce product pirating, using excel software to prepare account ledger, graphics software usage to increase staff creativity and decision support system software for board meetings all influence entrepreneurship activities. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on decision support skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities

Extent of Hardware Management Skill for Entrepreneurship Development

Table 3 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. However, the respondents identified that using UPS to backup computer from power failure, the use of key board to input figures into computer, using scanner to convert hard copy material to soft copy, use of accessory cables to link computer components to another and using speakers to hear DVD sound from the computer after seminar, all influence entrepreneurship activities. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on hardware management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities

Extent of Software Management Skill for Entrepreneurship Development

Table 4 revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, they were accepted as the extent software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities. However, the respondents identified that using spreadsheet for staff salaries preparation processes, using desktop publishing for business documentation, facilitators ability to organize online seminars for their customers, using graphic software for staff training and using database software to generate instructions, all influence entrepreneurship activities. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on the extent of software management skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated Information and Communication Technology skills acquired by office management and technology postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State universities. The researcher has in the process investigated four components of Information and Communication Technology skills which involved transaction processing skill, decision support skill, hardware management skill and software management skill for entrepreneurship in Rivers State Universities. The findings of the study among others revealed that all the items had mean above the criterion mean of 2.5 while the hypotheses revealed that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of RSU and IAUE of Office Management and Technology students on transaction processing skill acquired by Office Management and Technology Postgraduate students for entrepreneurship development in Rivers State Universities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

1. Teachers should expose Office Management and Technology students to transaction processing skill in order to influence entrepreneurship programme.

2. Teachers should expose Office Management and Technology students to decision support skill in order to influence entrepreneurship programme.
3. Teachers should expose Office Management and Technology students to hardware management skill in order to influence entrepreneurship programme.
4. Teachers should expose Office Management and Technology students to software management skill in order to influence entrepreneurship programme.

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